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Risk and Assessment in a Changing World

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Climate change and Mental Health in a changing world (example from Serbia)

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Abstract: We have experienced big changes of environment and also societal disruption due to local and regional disasters, pandemic and climate change. Communities and institutions have experienced great challenges, danger, consequences in human resources, and also infrastructure, so it is important to develop new approaches for risk assessment.

Infodemia, mental health risks in novel circumstances, impulse requirement to deal with complex and uncertain problems, increase transparency in science-to-policy processes, new skills and expertise.

Climate change as a chronic disaster (with rising temperatures, heatwaves, floods, droughts, fires, and loss of forest) directly and indirectly cause consequences on health and wellbeing, physical and mental.

Increases in extreme and heavy precipitation have expanded the risk of river flooding in many countries in Europe, including the Western Balkan region. Flooding affects human health through disrupting physical health, but also lead to mental health consequences. Disruption of health services, safe water/sanitation, and transportation ways, plays a major role in vulnerability. Studies show that when people experience feelings of loss, helplessness, depression, frustration and anxiety caused by their inability to cope with climate change and disasters, and other mental health challenges. In response to growing depression and (eco)anxiety, public health experts and psychotherapists are suggesting a new field of treatment, termed “eco-psychotherapy”.

Examples from Serbia and wider (WB region) after the 2014 floods underlined the importance of mental health services in a long-term period after the disaster, even if the house is compensated. We are in a similar situation in 2023 in some regions of Serbia, so these severe flooding again warned that climate change could make these occurrences more common.

Recovery actions after floods usually are limited to one or two years, but recovery of mental health needs more time. Lessons learned from Covid-19 crisis (which is still current) shows the urgent need to take care of mental health as one of the priorities in public health.

Developing and applying methods to preserve mental health in strengthening community resilience to disasters is essential for sustainable communities, as well as prevention and resilience.